

The Need for Predictive Risk Assessment for Plastics to Support Safe and Sustainable by Design

Executive Summary

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are increasingly detected in environmental and biological systems, raising concerns about their potential long-term impacts on human health and ecosystems. Despite growing awareness, significant knowledge gaps and uncertainties remain regarding their persistence, bioaccumulation, and detrimental interactions within biological systems. However, as our experience with other classes of synthetic substances, such as CFCs and their ozone-depleting effects, has shown, originally harmless substances can exhibit dangerous properties with dramatic consequences in certain environments. To avoid such unpleasant surprises, prospective risk assessment approaches are necessary to enable a risk-minimizing and sustainable design of new materials and thereby support the Safe and Sustainable by Design Strategy (SSbD) and Circular Economy Action Plan of the EU (European Commission 2020; 2022).

One of the aims of the **PlasticsFatE** (Plastics Fate and Effects in the Human Body) Project, supported by Horizon 2020, was to develop a risk assessment and management strategy for plastics based on a Decision Support System (DSS). Developing this tool has shown which knowledge gaps still exist and limit the use of current risk assessment approaches for plastics. This policy brief summarizes the difficulties we still face in the development and application of risk assessment tools and formulates research tasks to enable robust and sustainable risk assessment and risk management for plastics in the future.

1. A Decision Support System for risk assessment and management of plastics (DSS)

Decision support for risk assessment of materials is already available for engineered nanomaterials (e.g. SUNDS - The Sustainable Nanotechnologies Project Decision Support System¹ or LICARA nanoSCAN²). Comparable approaches are still lacking for plastics although they have been in use for a much longer time. The aim of the DSS is to close this gap for MNPs by providing guidelines for risk analysis and risk management. The DSS developed in PlasticsFatE is intended to support the following:

- Hazard assessment using tiered strategies and predictive models
- Exposure estimation via environmental and occupational models
- Anticipatory risk assessment during early material design stages

While the development process has underscored the persistence of data and knowledge gaps, the DSS already incorporates a set of functional tools—including a physiology based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model, models for environmental fate, occupational exposure and the prospective multi-criteria decision support tool (PMCDs) – even if there are gaps in data and knowledge. These elements not only allow for a first assessment of plausible risk scenarios but also provide a means to assess the degree of uncertainty associated with them. In doing so, the DSS helps to identify critical areas for further research and supports the broader implementation of SSbD principles in the development of future plastic materials.

¹<https://sunds.gd/>

²<http://www.nanosafer.org>

2. Current limitations of risk assessment approaches

The obstacles encountered during the development of the DSS made it clear that such risk assessment approaches are currently still limited in their functionality due to shortcomings in terms of data gaps and also methodology in the field of MNP research. The main reasons include:

- Knowledge gaps regarding types, concentrations and leaching behaviour of additives and residual chemicals from polymer synthesis
- Lack of comparable and quality-assured exposure and hazard data for most common polymers, whereby the proportion of nanoplastics is equally addressed
- Knowledge gaps regarding typical chemical and biological contaminants depending on the fate of the MNPs in the environment or the human body

Other reasons such as knowledge deficits with regard to the ageing of MNPs, mixture effects of associated chemicals and possible long-term effects increase the complexity of the task of assessing the risk of MNPs. For these reasons, the derivation of general statements about the risk of certain plastics or the risk of MNPs resulting from their use is still limited.

Figure 1 *Data gaps and methodological shortcomings that currently limit the risk assessment of MNPs.*

3. Research priorities to enable (prospective) risk assessment and support SSbD for plastics

The current barriers for risk assessment of MNPs require the following research priorities:

- a. Exposure and hazard assessment for a) polymer particles and b) plastic associated chemicals using harmonized/standardized methods and representative test and reference materials.
- b. Investigation of the joint effects of MNP and associated chemicals and contaminants.
- c. Investigation of long-term effects of MNPs and effects on vulnerable populations and ecosystems.
- d. Derivation of critical criteria as early risk indicators to support the safe and sustainable design of plastics.

4. Adopting a precautionary approach for risk management in the absence of necessary data

Given the substantial scientific uncertainty surrounding the environmental and health effects of MNPs, the precautionary principle provides a critical framework for early regulatory intervention. This principle, which asserts that lack of full scientific certainty should not delay cost-effective measures to prevent environmental degradation (European Commission, 2000), is particularly relevant in light of evidence that MNPs can cross biological barriers, persist in ecosystems, and potentially disrupt cellular and physiological functions (see PlasticsFatE Policy Briefs 2¹ & 3²). While comprehensive risk assessment is currently hindered by methodological and data limitations—including insufficient understanding of long-term exposure effects, mixture toxicity, and degradation behaviour—a precautionary stance supports the implementation of prospective risk assessment strategies. Integrating this principle into the early design and regulation of plastic materials can guide innovation toward safer alternatives and prevent irreversible damage, aligning with the broader goals of SSbD.

As long as the risk assessment for plastics and especially MNPs is limited, a precautionary strategy for the further control of plastics is all the more necessary, taking into account the following:

1. Risk Mitigation and Public Awareness:
 - a. Ensure the use of environmentally friendly additives and degradable polymers in particular for applications where release is unavoidable, such as tyres and facade paints.
 - b. Corporate Responsibility: Encourage businesses to minimize plastic footprints in packaging and through waste management best practices.
 - c. Consumer Guidance and Product Labelling: Make the hazard potential of additives in the individual plastics transparent for users and inform users about possibilities to reduce exposure through lifestyle changes, such as avoiding single-use plastics and using water filters.
2. International Collaboration:
 - a. Global Agreements: Establish international treaties to address plastic pollution, focusing on transboundary impacts of MNPs.
 - b. Shared Databases: Create repositories for research data to facilitate global collaboration and knowledge exchange, and the effective use of research funding.

Precautionary Measures during Development and the Life Cycle

Figure 2 The ambivalent relationship between high design freedom but large knowledge gaps in early phases of research and development (green) and the more extensive knowledge but disadvantageous path dependencies in later phases of product development and use (blue). Precautionary measures to minimize the risk potential of MNPs are assigned to the phases.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15119349>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/15119466>

Summary

The findings from **PlasticsFatE** and from similar studies within the EU CUSP cluster provide a foundation for informed decision-making, but additional investment and collaboration is essential to further develop the approaches established so far and fill existing knowledge gaps. Taking decisive action now will safeguard future generations from the unknown long-term consequences of micro- and nanoplastic exposure for human and environmental health.

Scientific uncertainty surrounding MNPs underscores the urgent need for expanded research and policy action. As a global leader in environmental regulation, the EU has a unique opportunity to drive forward a science-based strategy that protects human health and ecosystems from emerging plastic contaminants. By increasing funding, standardizing methodologies, and strengthening regulatory oversight, the EU can ensure an adequate and precautionary response to the risks posed by MNPs.

References

European Commission (2000) Communication from the Commission on the precautionary principle. COM/2000/0001 final, Document 52000DC0001

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52000DC0001>

European Commission (2020) A New Circular Economy Action Plan For a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, COM/2020/98 final

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>

European Commission (2022) Establishing a European Assessment Framework for 'Safe and Sustainable by Design' Chemicals and Materials, Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510, Document 32022H2510 C/2022/8854

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022H2510>

